

Evaluation of the Application of high Weight Materials for Structural Overloading in Building Construction A Case Study of Anambra State

By

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Abstract

The research is based on the influence of construction materials weight for structural overload in buildings, to assessment the use of high weight materials for structural overloading in building construction. The reviewed literature shows that the case study hasn't ascertain the study area which serves as the knowledge gap in this study. The application of questionnaires, walk around evaluation, use of primary data, secondary data and statistical tools like normal probability were employed to ascertain the impact of high weight materials and its influence as construction materials. From the findings, the results show that high weight materials have significant influence as construction materials which lead to structural overload in buildings, building failure, building crack, building deterioration and building collapse. The construction industries and practicing professionals have been urged to evaluate the use of high weight materials for structural overloading in buildings and in construction industries specifically as it concern in the Case study in Anambra State. From the results of investigations and analysis carried out, it could be concluded that the aim and objectives of this research have been achieved.

Keywords: Structural Overload, Building, Construction, High weight, Materials, crack & collapse

1. Introduction

Structural loads or actions are forces, deformations, or accelerations applied to a structure or its components (ASCE/SEI 7-05, 2006; Avallone & Baumeister, 2017). Loads cause stresses, deformations, and displacements in structures. Assessment of their effects is carried out by the methods of structural analysis. Excess load or overloading may cause structural failure, and hence such possibility should be either considered in the design or strictly controlled. Buildings are designed to support certain loads without deforming excessively. The loads are the weights of people and objects, the weight of rain and snow, in temperate and rigid climatic zones and the pressure of wind--called live loads--and the dead load of the building itself. With buildings of a few floors, strength generally accompanies sufficient rigidity, and the design is mainly that of a roof that will keep the weather out while spanning large open spaces. With tall buildings of many floors, the roof is a minor matter, and the support of the weight of the building itself is the main consideration. Like long bridges, tall buildings are subject to catastrophic collapse. The causes of structural overloading and building collapse can be classified under general headings to facilitate analysis. These are bad design, faulty construction, foundation failure, extraordinary load, unexpected failure mode and a combination of causes. Bad design does not mean only errors of computation, but a failure to take into account the loads the structure will be called upon to carry, erroneous theories, reliance on inaccurate data, ignorance of the effects of repeated or impulsive stresses, and improper choice of materials or misunderstanding of their properties. The engineer is responsible for these failures, which are created on the drawing board. Faulty construction has been the most important cause of structural overload. The engineer is also at fault here, if the inspection has been lax. This includes the use of salty sand to make concrete, the substitution of inferior steel for that specified, bad bolting or even improper tightening torque of nuts, excessive use of the drift pin to make holes line up, bad welds, and other practices well known to the construction worker. Even an excellently designed and constructed structure will not stand on a bad foundation. Although the structure will carry its loads, the earth beneath it may not. The Leaning Tower of Pisa is a famous example of bad foundations, but there are many others. The old armory in St. Paul, Minnesota, sank 20 feet or more into soft clay but did not collapse (Brackbill

et al, 2006). The displacements due to bad foundations may alter the stress distribution significantly. This was such a problem with railway bridges in America that statically determinate trusses were greatly preferred since they were not subject to this danger. Extraordinary loads are often natural, such as repeated heavy snowfalls, or the shaking of an earthquake, or the winds of a hurricane. A building that is intended to stand for some years should be able to meet these challenges. A flimsy flexible structure may avoid destruction in an earth movement, while a solid masonry building would be destroyed. Earth movement may cause foundation problems when moist filled land liquefies. Unexpected failure modes are the most complex of the reasons for the collapse. Any new type of structure is subject to unexpected failure until its properties are well understood (Brackbill et al, 2006; Turker & San, 2004). The conservative, strong statically determinate trusses were designed with pin-connected eye bars to be as strong and safe as possible. The column bends outward, or buckles and the load crashes to earth (Schweier & Markus, 2006). Tall buildings have generally been made with a rigid steel skeleton, sheathed in the lightest materials to keep out the weather. Alternatively, reinforced concrete, where the compression-resisting and protecting concrete surrounds the tough, tension-resisting steel, integrated into a single body, has been used. Such structures have never failed, and stoutly resist demolition. When the lower supports of a steel skeleton are destroyed, the weight of the building seems to crush the lower parts and the upper parts descend slowly into the pile of debris. Monolithic reinforced-concrete buildings are difficult to demolish in any fashion.

1.1 Research Aim

The aim of the research work is to ascertain the influence of construction materials weight for structural overload in buildings

1.2 Research Objectives

1. To ascertain whether structural overload causes failure on building construction
2. To investigate the effect of heavy weight materials in building deterioration
3. To ascertain whether heavy weight materials cause structural overload in buildings
4. To study whether structural overload cause cracks in buildings
5. To ascertain whether structural overload cause building collapse in construction

1.3 Research Questions

The following research questions were outlined in the cause of this study and as listed below:

1. Can structural overload cause failure on building construction?
2. Is the any significant effect of heavy weight materials in building deterioration?
3. Does heavy weight materials cause structural overload in building constructions?
4. Does structural overload cause cracks in buildings?
5. Does structural overload causes building collapse in construction?

1.4 Hypothesis of the Study

The following hypotheses were developed in the study.

- i. H_i : heavy weight materials causes building failure due to structural overload
 H_o : heavy weight materials does not cause building failure due to structural overload
- ii. H_i : there is significant effect of heavy weight materials in building deterioration
 H_o : there is no significant effect of heavy weight materials in building deterioration
- iii. H_i : heavy weight materials cause structural overload in building constructions
 H_o : heavy weight materials does not cause structural overload in building constructions
- iv. H_i : structural overload cause cracks in buildings
 H_o : structural overload does not cause cracks in buildings
- v. H_i : structural overload cause building collapse in construction
 H_o : structural overload does not cause building collapse in construction

2 Review of Related Literatures

For many existing building structures there is a need to change the purpose of the building during the service life and the load carrying capacity can vary (Ezeokonkwo, Ezeliora, and Mbanusi, 2019). Nowadays, many buildings are being rebuilt to provide other functions than originally designed for. However, the knowledge about the former usage is often incomplete, often due to insufficient documentation of the previous design and utilization, usage and handling. It also happens that building structures have been damaged in the past due to overloading or high loads in combination with mistakes in execution or handling (John, 2013). This may lead to

uncertainties about the future use of the building and its residual load carrying capacity. Then the structure can be prevented to be reused for other purposes in the future. A project concerning new loads on an existing column supported flat slab was to be carried out. However, during an inspection of the worksite a large amount of wide cracks was found, mainly around columns in the top of the slab (Mehndi, Khan, and Ahmad, 2014). Such cracks are natural. However, such wide cracks were unexpected. Such observations in existing structures question the ability to expose the structure to specified loads in the future. The main issue is how to assess the cause of the observed damage in terms of past overloading? If so, how to estimate the remaining load carrying capacity? Can the observed orientation, localization and width of cracks give answer concerning the questionable remaining performance?

2.1 Loads and Stress

Internal and external forces act on structural components. An external force is commonly referred to as a load; an internal force is a stress. Another way to look at it is action and reaction. The load is the action; the stress is the reaction. For every action, there is an equal and opposite reaction. The load applied to a column would place the column in compression; conversely, a load hanging from a rod would place the rod in tension. Strain is the deformation of a structural member because of stress within the member. Stress is usually measured in terms of Newton per millimeter. Strain is measured in the percentage of elongation that happens when the material is tensioned (Jay, 2018). Compression is a crushing force. Tension is a pulling force that is trying to make the building material longer. Shear attempts to make the building materials or structural components slide past one another (Ezeliora, Adinna, and Ezenwa, 2018). In shear tests, force is applied to pull the materials apart. Use of a concrete anchor is an example of shear resistance. When the anchor is placed in a hole in the concrete, a bolt or screw is inserted and tightened. The tightening causes the anchor to swell. Shear resistance keeps the anchor in the concrete. The common nail is another type of building fastener that resists the forces of shear. A gang-nail plate used on a lightweight wooden truss somewhat resists shear (John, 2013). Structural members that are under a load must change shape. If the member does not change shape, no load is present. The force applied causes this change in shape. In most structures, the eye will not

detect the change in shape when the structural member is carrying a normal load (Mehndi, Khan, and Ahmad, 2014).

2.2 Empirical Review

Montepara *et al.* (2001) showed the use of geo foam is a suitable alternative to natural aggregates to be used for construction of embankment standing on soft subgrade. Geo foam offers the possibility to have a very light structure avoiding all the problems related to the settlement of the embankment foundation. This is especially true when rapid road rehabilitation is required in order to solve the severe problems related to landslide phenomena. Alan (1990) and Amobi (2006) identified building components as capable of failing in structure, function and aesthetics. Amobi (2006) classified factors that contribute to sub-structural components failures to include differential settlement of foundation, shear and plastic failures and design failures; and the super structural components failures to include overloading, bulking, natural disaster, poor structural design, inferior materials, poor workmanship and overloading. Ayininuola and Olalusi (2004) identified factors contributing to building failure as including the use of substandard materials and engagement of quacks rather than professionals by clients in an attempt to cut down construction cost. Olajumoke *et al.* (2006) identified causes of structural failure in slabs to inadequate thickness and inadequate reinforcement. The work of Freddy (1999) was on maintenance measure of buildings. These studies did not, however, assess the failure of the individual components and the specific causes of failure of the components. Adejimi (2005) opined that more effort during the design stage could help to prevent or reduce unnecessary maintenance problems that can come up later in the life of a building. Jaydeep and Bhavin (2018), reveal the conceptual study of construction defects, structural overloads and structural failures, its occurrences during the design and construction. The researchers suggest solutions and means of eliminating the problems in building and constructions. Reinforced concrete is widely used as a structural material due to its long lifespan, although as all building materials it also has limited design service life. Once a reinforced concrete structure is approaching the end of its design service life, a decision has to be made whether the building should be demolished and replaced or rather repaired and strengthened. Due to rising importance of sustainability in built society, repair costs and increasing focus on waste recycling, it is preferable to bring

structures back to their original performance (Urs *et al.*, 2015). While noticing cracks at the face of structural components, rust stains, spalling or excessive deflection is quite easy, it is still very important but difficult to find reasons for their occurrence. Service life may be reduced by many various circumstances: mistakes in the design, errors in execution or by overloading the structure (Holický *et al.*, 2013), (Banville, 2008). In order to find out what has caused any damage to a structure it is valuable to conduct a document survey. Specifications, plans, photographs, other structural documentation and even interviews may provide information about a building's history, sometimes very essential in finding the cause of the problem (Banville, 2008).

3 Primary Data

Primary data is the information gathered directly by the researcher. For the purpose of this research primary data was collected through questionnaire, oral interviews, direct observations and walkthrough evaluations.

3.1 Secondary Data

Secondary data is a synthesis of published and unpublished documents related to the study, and comprises the logical frame work of the study. The collected secondary data, therefore, included the most relevant and current, within the discipline from text books, academic articles, journals and magazines. A number of online sources were also used to get information for literature review.

3.2 Questionnaire

This study is a case study and as such required information from a large population. Questionnaires have some value in case-studies when straight forward and fairly accurate information is required from a large population. In this study as much information as possible is required from a large population of staff and students in the study University. Questionnaires are data gathering devices designed to elicit answers or reactions to rearranged questions presented in a specific order. The questionnaires designed for this study was both structured and semi-structured questionnaires (multiple choices) and included both open ended and closed ended questions. The open ended questions allowed respondents to freely express their opinions and

views without prejudices so that adequate information is obtained in relation to the objectives of the study. A total of one hundred and sixty (160) questionnaires were distributed to staff and students by the researcher and research assistants by hand. Out of the 160 questionnaires, distributed, 148 were returned which is 92.5% response rate. See table 1:

3.3 Population of the Study

Preliminary survey of the study revealed that a total of sixty (60) building structures, comprising of twenty (20) in Awka, five (5) in Nnewi twelve (12) in Oko, seven (7) in Ekwulobia and fifteen (15) in Agulu were in the study area.

According to available records from some construction company staff, contractors, engineers, building material sellers and construction laborers formed the population of this study. This groups are considered to be experienced enough to provide informed opinion about the structural overload in buildings within the state of study. Therefore, the population for this study covered sixty (60) building structures in the study areas.

3.4 Sampling Techniques

For high degree of accuracy and adequacy in representation of the sample, the researcher employed two sampling techniques namely: stratified random sampling for administration of the questionnaire in the survey aspect of the study while purposive sampling technique was used for the selection of company staff, construction laborers, contractors, structural consultancies and engineers. The use of stratified random sampling technique is justifiable because it reduces sampling error (Ezeliora, Adinna, and Ezenwa, 2018; Ezeokonkwo, Ezeliora, and Mbanusi, 2019) illustrates that stratified random sampling improves the representativeness of the sample in terms of variables used in the stratification, and can be used to select a sample of this study. Purposive sampling is a non-probability technique that selects informative subjects or units of observation as a representation of the wider relatively cost effective, easier, and ensures that only those elements that are relevant to the study are included.

3.5 Determination of Sample Size

The sample size for this study was determined using Bouely’s formular:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

when n = sample size

N = population

e² = Margin of error (assumed 5%)

1 = unity or constant

$$\text{Therefore} = \frac{268}{1+268(0.05)^2}$$

$$\frac{268}{1+(268 \times 0.0025)}$$

$$\frac{268}{1 + 3.25}$$

$$\frac{268}{1.67} = 160$$

The sample size of 160 was adopted for this study.

Table 1 Distribution of Questionnaire

Group	Campuses	
	Total	%
Company Staff	70	44
Laborers	30	19
Contractors	19	12
Engineers	25	15
Building consultancies	16	10
Sub Total	160	100%

Source: Researcher’s field study (2024)

3.6 Method of Data Analysis

The data generated for this study were analyzed with appropriate statistical techniques. The techniques included frequency, percentages and mean score. The hypotheses postulated were put

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in null (H_0). All analysis was done using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 21. The hypotheses were tested using Pearson Correlation Coefficient, Kendall tau rank correlation coefficient, one way ANOVA, student T-test, mean score and spearman correlation coefficient.

4 Data Presentation, Analysis and Interpretation

The presentation, analysis and interpretation of all the data collected are presented and analyzed in this chapter. They are based on the objectives, research questions and hypotheses that guided the research.

Distribution of Questionnaire

Table 2 Return Rate of Questionnaire

Questionnaire	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Total No of Questionnaire Administered	160	00.00
No of Questionnaire Received	148	92.5
No of Questionnaire not Received	12	7.5
Total		100%

Source: Researchers field survey 2024

4.1.1 Number of Questionnaire Distributed and Returned

Table 2 shows that a total number of 160 questionnaires were distributed to the respondents based on a stratified random sampling. Out of the 160 questionnaire distributed, 148 were completed and returned which corresponds to a response rate of 92.5%. The response rate was high because research assistants were used by the researcher in distributing and returning the questionnaire. The response rate of 92.5% is therefore reasonably high and adequate for the study. The rest of the questionnaire were either not properly completed or returned uncompleted. The ones not properly completed were disregarded because they were not usable. No reason was

given by the respondents for the uncompleted questionnaire. Table 3 shows the population distribution of respondents and the percentage response to the questionnaires by the respondents.

Table 3: Population Distribution of Questionnaires to various professionals and percentage of response

Name of Professional	No of Questionnaire Distributed	No of Received Questionnaire	Percentage (%) of Response
Architects	40	38	26
Estate Management	24	22	15
Engineers	15	12	8
Builders	45	42	28
Surveyors	36	34	23
Total	160	148	100

Source: Researchers field survey 2024

Table 3 shows that a total 148 questionnaires distributed to various professionals in the construction industry. The rate of response from various professional were as follows: Architects 38 questionnaires were returned which was 26 percent, Estate Management 22 questionnaire were returned and this showed 15 percent of questionnaires returned, Engineers 12 questionnaire were returned and this showed 8 percent of questionnaires returned, Builders 42 questionnaires were returned at 28 percent and the fourth profession, surveyors 34 questionnaires were returned which is 23 percent of the questionnaire returned.

Table 4 Respondents' Gender for Construction Staff

Gender	Number of Responses	Percentage (%)
Male	97	66
Female	51	34
Total	148	100%

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4.2 Respondents Responses on Gender

Table 4 shows that 97 of the respondents representing 66% are males, while 51 respondents representing 34% are females. This shows an over-representation of male respondents in the survey. However, it does reflect the Nigerian construction industry system is dominated by male staff.

Table 5 Respondents’ Professional Registration Status

Professional Registration	Not Registered members	Percentage
ARCON	35	24
CORBON	39	26
COREN	9	6
OSRBOW	20	14
OTHERS	45	30
	148	100

Source: Researchers field survey 2024

Table 5 shows that out of the 148 professionals that returned the questionnaire 70 percent of the respondents were fully registered with their respective professional bodies. The distribution is in the order state below:

ARCON	24 Percent
CORBON	26 Percent
COREN	6 Percent
OSRBON	14 Percent
OTHERS	30 Percent

This shows that a greater percentage of the questionnaires returned were handled by persons professionally judged as being competent by various professional bodies.

Table 6 Respondents’ years of Experience

Years of Experience	No Respondent	Percentage
Less than 5 years	12	8
5 – 14 years	58	39
15 – 20 years	47	32
Above 20 years	31	21
Total	148	100

Source: Researchers field survey 2024

Table 6 shows that the respondents were well experienced in the field that they could make useful contributions in the study. Respondents with less than 5 years were 12 respondents with 8 percent of the total respondents. Respondents with over 5 to 14 years were 58 respondents with 39 percent of the total respondents. A total of 47 respondents have between 15 to 20 years of experience with 32 percent. Respondents with over 20 years were 31 respondents with 21 percent of the total respondents.

Table 7: Academic Qualification

Variables	No of Responses	Percentages
(a) Ph.D.	17	12
(b) M.Sc	40	27
(c) B.Sc/B Eng	59	40
(d) HND	21	14
(e) Others	11	7
Total	148	100%

Source: Researchers field survey 2024

Respondents of Academic Qualification

Table 7 highlights of the academic qualification of the respondents. In terms of their academic qualification, the table indicates that majority of the 59 respondents representing 40% have first degrees, followed by 40 (27%) who have M.Sc. 17 (12%) respondents obtained Ph.D. and the remaining respondents which represents 21 (14%) obtained HND and other qualifications

recognized by the institution has 11 respondents representing 7% of the respondents. This highlights that the respondents are educated enough to handle maintenance operations.

Table 8: Hypothesis Response Analysis on the influence of construction materials weight to structural overload in buildings

S/N	Analysis of the Hypothesis Response	Responses	Frequency	Percentage
1	Heavy weight materials causes building failure due to structural overload	Yes	146	98.65
		No	2	1.35
	Total		148	100
2	There is significant effect of heavy weight materials in building deterioration	Yes	138	93.24
		No	10	6.76
	Total		148	100
3	Heavy weight materials cause structural overload in building constructions	Yes	148	100
		No	0	0
	Total		148	100
4	Structural overload cause cracks in buildings	Yes	130	87.84
		No	18	12.16
	Total		148	100
5	Structural overload cause building collapse in construction	Yes	137	92.57
		No	11	7.43
	Total		148	100

Table 8 shows the Response Analysis on the influence of construction materials weight to structural overload in buildings. The table above shows that majority of the respondent accept their alternative hypothesis while very few of the respondent accept the null hypothesis. In the first hypothesis, 146 (98.65%) out of 148 respondent accept the alternative while 2 (1.35%) respondents accept the null. In second hypothesis, 138 out of 148 respondent accept the alternative while 10 respondents accept the null hypothesis. The third hypothesis shows that 148 (100%) out of 148 respondent accept the alternative while 0 (0%) respondents accept the null.

The fourth hypothesis shows that 130 (87.84%) out of 148 respondents accept the alternative while 18 (12.16%) respondents accept the null. The fifth hypothesis shows that 137 (92.57%) out of 148 respondents accept the alternative while 11 (7.43%) respondents accept the null.

Figure 1: Probability Plot of Frequency

Figure 1 shows the normality of the data collected from the questionnaire. The normal probability plot reveals the significant rate of the data collected from the questionnaire responses. The plot shows that the data collected is significant with significance level of less than 0.005. This shows that the data collected is fit for statistical analysis and its fit for the purpose of its analysis

5.1 Summary of key Findings

- (1) The research respondents covered both construction staff and contractors and comprised of males and females, while males were more in number.

- (2) Majority of staff and contractors work within the case study in Anambra state.
- (3) The staff is mainly professionals possessing educational qualification mostly up to Master's degree and PhD. They are affiliated with various professional bodies.
- (4) There are insufficient competent staff and contractors to mind those sections of materials weight for structural overload in buildings
- (5) There is need for construction staff and contractors to be part of the design and supervision team at inception and completion of any new building.
- (6) There is need for training and continuous development programmes for construction staff and contractors for materials weight for structural overload in buildings
- (7) Some builders and building designers does not use Computerization technique to evaluate materials weight for structural overload in buildings.
- (8) Poor structural buildings and overload affect buildings and can cause building crack or collapse.
- (9) Heavy weight materials causes building failure due to structural overload
- (10) There is significant effect of heavy weight materials in building deterioration
- (11) Heavy weight materials cause structural overload in building constructions
- (12) Structural overload cause cracks in buildings
- (13) Structural overload cause building collapse in construction

5.3 Conclusions

In conclusion, the research is based on the influence of construction materials weight for structural overload in buildings, to assessment the use of high weight materials for structural overloading in building construction. Response of the respondents showed that forthe influence of construction materials weight for structural overload in buildings heavy weight materials causes building failure, building crack, building collapse. The research was carried in Anambra state. Heavy weight materials cause building failure due to structural overload. There is significant effect of heavy weight materials in building deterioration. However, the research revealed that Structural overload cause cracks and collapse in building constructions. The construction industries and practicing professionals have been urged to adopt and to assessment

the use of high weight materials for structural overloading in buildings and in construction industries specifically as it concern in the Case study in Anambra State. From the results of investigations and analysis carried out, it could be concluded that the aim and objectives of this research have been achieved.

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